

ON THE VITAMIN-C AND CAROTENE CONTENT OF SEVERAL HERBS AND FLOWERS USED IN AYURVEDIC SYSTEM OF MEDICINE

BY N. M. BASU, G. K. RAY AND N. K. DE

Of the various herbs etc. examined, mature "Neem" leaves are very rich, tender Neem leaves, Vasak, Dhania and Babla thorn leaves are quite rich, both in carotene and vitamin-C and Pudina, Kukshima, Amrul, Durba grass, Gandal leaves are quite rich in carotene only. The vitamin-C content of Nishinda, Shiull, Visalya-karani and Kukshima leaves increases very greatly after frying in oil.

This investigation was undertaken with a view to throwing light on the possible relationship between the medicinal properties of these herb, etc, and their vitamin-C and carotene contents.

Vitamin-C and carotene were extracted and estimated in the same way as was done in the case of mangoes (Basu, Ray and De, *this Journal*, 1947, 24. 355) As in the course of preparation of medicines from these herbs, some of them are fried in oil and subjected to other forms of heat treatment, the alteration in the vitamin-C content of some of them after heat treatment has been noted. The results of estimation are given in the accompanying table.

It is curious that mature *neem* leaves, which are used extensively in the preparation of medicines for the healing of obstinate sores, are very rich in both vitamin-C and carotene, but tender leaves, which are taken either in soup or after frying, contain much less vitamin-C and carotene. *Vasak* leaves and their extract are said to be efficacious in cough and cold. They are also rich in both vitamin-C and carotene. *Dhania* (coriander) leaves are widely taken in Bengal. They are found to be rich both in vitamin-C and carotene and their use should be encouraged. *Babla* thorn leaves are not consumed but are used for poultice over abscesses. They are rich both in vitamin-C and carotene. If the vitamin-C or carotene content or both of these leaves were an index of their sore-healing properties, then all those leaves, which are rich in both, should be experimented upon for this purpose. *Pudina* leaves, which are eaten raw, are quite rich in carotene, but not in vitamin-C. The leaves which are rich in carotene are *Neem*, *Pudina*, *Dhania*, *Babla*, *Kukshima*, *Amrul*, *Gandal* etc. Remembering that the optimal daily requirements of vitamin-C and vitamin-A or carotene are 60 mg. and 4000 I. U. or γ (micro-gramme), one can easily find out from the list appended (Table I) how much of these vitamins he can get from these articles when consumed.

A noteworthy feature of some of these herbs, particularly *Nishinda*, *Shinli*, *Visalya-karani* and *Kukshima*, is that the vitamin-C content instead of being decreased by frying in oil, increases considerably. The percentage increase or decrease of vitamin-C after heat treatment has been shown in the table. Increase in vitamin-C content on heat treatment in vegetables has been previously shown by various workers in India and abroad and Dr. B. C. Guha has given the name of ascorbigen to the substance which is converted into vitamin-C on heating.

TABLE I

No.	Name of samples.	Bot. names.	*Free vitamin-C (mg. per 100 g.)	% Increase or decrease after the heat treatment.	Carotene in γ per 100 g.
1.	Neem leaves (mature)	<i>Melia azadirachta</i>	400.0		7500.0
	Do .. (tender)		300.0		} 3400.0 1250.0
2.	Vaank leaves (mature)	<i>Adhatoda vasica</i>	250.0		
	Do (another sample)		188.0 (89.0)	48.0 (decrease)	
3.	Dhania leaves	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	250.0		5200.0
	Do (another sample)		83.0 (83.0)	Nil	
4.	Babla kanta (leaves)	<i>Acacia arabica</i>	200.0		4800.0
5.	Nishinda leaves	<i>Vitex negundo</i>	150.0		3500.0
	Do (another variety)		80.0 (120.0)	100.0 (increase)	
6.	Durba grass	<i>Cynodere dactylon</i>	150.0		4800.0
7.	Marigold flower	<i>Tagetes patula</i>	135.0		
	Do (another variety)		25.0		
8.	Marigold leaves		180.0		
9.	Shinli leaves	<i>Nyctanthes arbor-tristis</i>	130.0		2000.0
	Do (another sample)		90.0 (80.0)	100.0 (increase)	
10.	Amrul rak	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i>	125.0		7600.0
11.	Amra	<i>Spondias mangifera</i>	100.0		
12.	Bel leaves	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	100.0		4500.0
13.	Gandal leaves	<i>Paspalum foetida</i>	100.0 (110.0)	10.0 (increase)	
	Do (another sample)		75.0		3800.0
14.	Tulsi leaves	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	80.0		2500.0
15.	Pathar kuchi leaves	<i>Bryophyllum calycium</i>	73.0 (43.0)	40.0 (decrease)	
	.. (another sample)		40.0		1800.0
16.	Kantakari	<i>Solanum ferox</i>	70.0		1800.0
17.	Bitter gourd (small) leaves	<i>Momordica charantia</i>	50.0 (59.0)	Practically nil	
	.. (another sample)		40.0		2400.0

TABLE I (contd.)

No.	Name of samples.	Bot. names.	*Free vitamin-C (mg. per 100 g.)	% Increase or decrease after the heat treatment.	Carotene in γ per 100 g.
18.	Arhar leaves	<i>Cajanus indica</i>	50.0		3100.0
19.	Haritaki	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	50.0		Nil
20.	Kalmegh	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i>	50.0 (40.0)	20.0 (increase)	
	Do (another sample)		Traces		3400.0
21.	Hincha leaves	<i>Ehrydra fluclians</i>	50.0		300.0
22.	Thalkuni leaves	<i>Hydrocotyl Japonica</i> or	40.0 (26.0)	10.0 (decrease)	
	Do (another sample)	Do <i>Asiatica</i>	20.0		2400.0
23.	Gulancha stick	<i>Tricospora cordifolias</i>	40.0		160.0
24.	Kakmachi leaves	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	40.0 (40.0)	Nil	
	Do (another sample)		20.0		2600.0
	Do seeds		20.0		240.0
25.	Punarnaba	<i>Boerhaavia rarpous</i>	30.0 (30.0)	23.0 (decrease)	
26.	Kukshima leaves	<i>Blumen laerra</i>	30.0 (50.0)	66.6 (increase)	
	Do (another sample)		Nil		4000.0
27.	Onion stalk	<i>Allium cepa</i>	30.0		260.0
28.	Kulatha Kanta (leaves)	—	20.0		2200.0
29.	Visalyakarani	<i>Eupatorium ayapana</i>	25.0 (50.0)	100.0 (increase)	2300.0
30.	Chalta	<i>Dellenia indica</i>	20.0		Traces
31.	Ghreetskumari	<i>Aloe perfoliata</i>	20.0		600.0
32.	Gok-khur seeds	<i>Tribulus cistoides</i>			
33.	Pudina	<i>Mentha sativa</i>	16.0		5400.0
34.	Shetpurni	<i>Trianthema monogynum</i>	15.0		2300.0
35.	Simul mul	<i>Bombax malabocicum</i>	Traces		Nil
36.	Aswagandha	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	Traces		
37.	Khet-pabra	<i>Mollugo stricta</i>	Traces		3600.0
38.	Jonki leaves		Traces		1600.0
39.	Pora mula		Traces		
40.	Dhutra leaves	<i>Datura stramonium</i> or <i>D. fastuosa</i>	Traces		3500.0
41.	Bahera	<i>Terminalia belerica</i>			Nil
42.	Figs	<i>Ficus histida</i>			Traces
43.	Satamul	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	Nil		Nil

* Figures in parentheses refer to those after frying.